

The Material Cost of Coastal Flooding: Property-Level Evidence from Danish Storm-Surge Insurance Claims

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Abstract

This paper provides property-level evidence on the drivers of material damage from residential storm-surge flooding. We use compensation records from the Danish Natural Damage Council for ten storm-surge events between 2013 and 2023, covering more than 6,000 claims. We link these records to the national Building and Dwelling Register and to a 0.4 m digital terrain model. For each compensated property, we reconstruct inundation depth from the elevation of flooded dwellings and model the insurance payout as a function of depth, building characteristics, storm event, and coastal zone. The payout captures compensated material damage and is therefore a lower bound on the full social cost of flooding. We estimate separate models for permanent houses and summer houses.

Inundation depth is a driver of damage. Payouts increase strongly with flood depth; increasing inundation from 1 m to 2 m is associated with roughly a 50–60% increase in payouts. Building size is also an important predictor: doubling the relevant size measure is associated with roughly 30–40% higher payouts. For permanent houses, a basement roughly doubles the payout, and timber walls increase payouts by 60–80% relative to brick walls. Construction era is at most a weak predictor once depth, size, and materials are controlled for. We also find persistent cost differences across storm events conditional on physical exposure, although the data cannot identify whether these differences reflect property composition, claims settlement, or repair-cost conditions. The estimates identify both which factors drive realised flood damage and by how much, providing empirical parameters that can be used to assess, refine, and recalibrate the assumptions embedded in existing flood-damage models.

Keywords: storm surge; flood damage; insurance claims; inundation depth; residential buildings; damage functions; climate adaptation

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1 Introduction

Extreme coastal water levels are projected to become more frequent and more severe across northern Europe during the twenty-first century as a consequence of anthropogenic climate change. Rising mean sea levels, combined with changes in storm-surge dynamics, are expected to increase the frequency and extent of coastal flooding (Colgan et al., 2022; Oppenheimer et al., 2019; Su, Andrée, Nielsen, Olsen, & Madsen, 2021; Vousdoukas, Mentaschi, Voukouvalas, Verlaan, & Feyen, 2017). Denmark is particularly vulnerable to these developments. Its long and low-lying coastline faces surges from both the North Sea and the Baltic Sea, and the past decade has brought several damaging events, including the December 2013 storm Bodil and the October 2023 Baltic surge. As coastal flood risk intensifies, understanding the economic consequences of storm-surge events for residential properties becomes increasingly important.

Reliable estimates of flood damages are essential for coastal adaptation planning. Decisions regarding investments in dikes, pumping infrastructure, managed retreat, and other adaptation measures are typically informed by cost–benefit analyses that compare implementation costs with expected reductions in flood losses. The validity of these assessments therefore depends critically on the accuracy of the underlying damage estimates. Mischaracterizing either the magnitude or the spatial distribution of flood damages may lead to inefficient adaptation decisions, resulting in overprotection, underprotection, or the misallocation of resources. Identifying the determinants of realized flood losses is thus a prerequisite for evidence-based adaptation policy.

Most flood-damage estimates used in practice are derived from synthetic damage models. These models commonly rely on depth–damage functions constructed from expert judgement, stylised assumptions regarding buildings and contents, and limited empirical calibration. Key assumptions—including the characteristics of the representative building, the valuation of structural and content damages, the influence of building attributes, and the functional relationship between inundation depth and losses—are often only partially observable (Abate, Panduro, Massenberg, & Arnbjerg-Nielsen, 2026; Goyal & Mukherjee, 2025). As a result, the empirical validity of many operational damage models remains difficult to assess, and independent validation is often limited.

Despite their importance, empirical analyses based on observed flood losses remain scarce. Existing studies either rely on post-event surveys or lack detailed information on property characteristics. One notable example is BN-FLEMOps, a probabilistic Bayesian network model that predicts flood losses using information on inundation depth, building characteristics, and household precautionary behaviour derived from post-event surveys (Lüdtke et al., 2019; Steinhausen, 2022). While valuable, such approaches rely on self-reported information regarding damages and household responses. Our analysis instead uses observed insurance compensation payments, providing a direct measure of realised and professionally assessed flood losses.

Another important contribution is Porter et al. (2023) who estimate depth–damage relationships using historical insurance claims data. However, their analysis is

largely limited to flood depth because detailed information on property characteristics is unavailable. By contrast, we link insurance compensation records to Denmark’s national Building and Dwelling Register (BBR), which provides detailed information on building size, age, use, construction characteristics, and other structural attributes. This enables us to examine not only the effect of inundation depth but also how differences in building characteristics contribute to variation in realised flood damages..

Our study therefore contributes to the literature in two ways. First, unlike survey-based approaches such as BN-FLEMOps, we analyse observed insurance compensation payments, avoiding potential biases associated with self-reported damages. Second, unlike previous insurance-based studies, we combine claims data with detailed building-register information, allowing a richer empirical analysis of the determinants of flood losses. Rather than developing a predictive machine-learning model, we employ transparent econometric methods to estimate the conditional relationships between realised damages, flood exposure, and property characteristics. This approach provides new evidence on the drivers of residential storm-surge losses and offers an empirical basis for evaluating the assumptions embedded in widely used flood-damage models.

The analysis is based on a unique dataset of property-level compensation payments from the Danish Natural Damage Council. The records cover the major Danish storm-surge events occurring between 2013 and 2023 and report assessed compensation for each affected property. We interpret compensation payments as measures of realised and compensated material damage, including repair and replacement of damaged structures and contents as well as temporary rehousing expenses. It is therefore a lower bound on the full social cost of flooding, which also includes non-market effects such as health impacts, mortality risk, lost time, damage to public infrastructure, ecosystem damage, and other uninsured or under-compensated losses.

We link the compensation records to the BBR and to a 0.4 m digital terrain model. Because inundation depth is not observed directly, we reconstruct local flood height from the elevations of the dwellings that were actually compensated. We then estimate the payout as a function of inundation depth, building size, basement presence, construction era, wall material, distance to water, storm event, and coastal zone. The models are estimated separately for permanent houses and summer houses, since the building stock and the damage mechanism differ across these segments.

The results identify inundation depth as the dominant determinant of compensated damage. Payouts increase strongly with flood depth; increasing inundation from 1 m to 2 m is associated with approximately a 50–60% increase in compensation. Building size is also an important predictor. For permanent houses, basements and non-brick wall materials are associated with substantially higher payouts, whereas construction era has little explanatory power once other building characteristics are controlled for. We also find systematic differences across storm events conditional on physical exposure, although the available data do not permit identification of the underlying mechanisms.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to analyse residential storm-surge

damages using property-level insurance compensation records linked to both detailed building-register data and reconstructed inundation depths. The primary contribution of the paper is empirical. By quantifying how realised damages vary with flood exposure and building characteristics, the analysis provides evidence that can be used to evaluate and refine the assumptions embedded in widely used storm-surge damage models. In particular, the results offer empirical guidance on the shape of the depth–damage relationship and the importance of building characteristics in explaining flood losses. As such, they contribute to the development of more credible damage estimates for coastal adaptation appraisal and cost–benefit analysis.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 describes the data and their construction, including the reconstruction of inundation depth. Section 3 presents the empirical strategy. Section 4 reports descriptive statistics. Section 5 presents the model estimates. Section 6 interprets the estimated effects, and Section 7 discusses the implications and limitations of the analysis.

2 Data

2.1 Overview

The analysis combines property-level storm-surge compensation records from the Danish Natural Damage Council with information from Denmark’s national Building and Dwelling Register (BBR). These records are further linked to geospatial data on terrain elevation and hydrological exposure. The unit of observation is a compensated residential property for which storm-surge damage was assessed and compensation awarded. The outcome variable is the monetary compensation paid for the reported damage.

2.2 Insurance claims and the payout measure

Compensation records were obtained from the Danish Natural Damage Council (Natureskaderådet, formerly Stormrådet), which administers Denmark’s statutory storm-surge compensation scheme. Under this scheme, all properties covered by fire insurance are automatically insured against storm-surge damage. Following an officially declared storm-surge event, reported damages are assessed and eligible losses compensated according to the provisions of the scheme (Natureskaderådet, 2025). Our primary outcome variable is the compensation payment awarded to each property. The compensation reflects the assessed cost of repairing or replacing damaged building structures and contents, net of the statutory deductible. In addition to the net payout, we construct a measure of gross material damage by adding back the applicable deductible, which differs between permanent dwellings and summer houses (Natureskaderådet, 2025). All monetary values are expressed in constant 2023 Danish kroner (DKK) using the annual average consumer price index reported by Statistics Denmark (Table PRIS8).

Throughout the paper, compensation payments are interpreted as measures of realised and compensated material damage. They capture the direct costs of repairing and replacing damaged property but do not include uninsured losses, non-market damages, or broader social impacts associated with flooding.

We identified the principal storm-surge events affecting Denmark over the period [2013–2023]¹: Bodil, Egon, Gorm, Urd, the January 2017 Baltic surge, Alfrida, Ingolf, Malik, the October 2023 Baltic surge, and Pia (Table 1). Claims relating to commercial properties (*Erhverv*) were excluded, restricting the analysis to residential dwellings.

2.3 The building and dwelling register and temporal matching

Structural and locational attributes are drawn from the Building and Dwelling Register (BBR). At the dwelling-unit level, BBR records floor area, number of rooms and bathrooms, number of floors, building footprint, construction and renovation year, exterior wall and roof materials, heating system, and the presence and size of a basement, together with point coordinates.

A central data challenge is that BBR is continuously updated and stores only the *current* state of each property: it is a snapshot of the present rather than a historical archive, so a property’s attributes at the time of a past event cannot be retrieved directly from the live register. We addressed this by assembling a set of archived BBR extracts — snapshots for 2011, 2015, 2016, 2018, 2020, 2022 and 2023 — and matching each event to the temporally closest snapshot (for example, the December 2013 Bodil event to the 2015 extract). The snapshots were harmonized to a common schema: variable names and coverage were reconciled across vintages, and attributes absent in a given year (notably the basement indicators) were imputed from the nearest available year by unit identifier. Property attributes therefore reflect the closest available snapshot rather than the exact event date. Given the register’s design this is the best feasible approximation.

2.4 Linking claims to the register

Compensation records identify a property by address but do not carry the BBR unit identifier, so claims were linked to dwellings through a staged address-matching procedure carried out within municipality and postcode. To focus on plausibly exposed properties and to bound the matching universe, candidate dwellings were restricted to those below 5 m elevation, above which direct storm-surge inundation is likely negligible. Addresses on both sides were standardized — lower-cased, with Danish characters transliterated ($\text{æ} \rightarrow \text{ae}$, $\text{ø} \rightarrow \text{oe}$, $\text{å} \rightarrow \text{aa}$), punctuation removed, and each string parsed into street name, house number, unit designation, postcode and city. Matching then proceeded in cascading

¹In Denmark storm events are named by the Danish Meteorological Institute and constitute a unique identifier of the event

stages of decreasing stringency: (i) an exact match on the full cleaned address; (ii) an exact match on postcode, municipality, street and house number, for claims lacking a unit designation; and (iii) a fuzzy match on street name (Jaro–Winkler string distance ≤ 0.12) conditional on an exact postcode, municipality and house-number match, which absorbs spelling errors without conflating different house numbers (Van der Loo, 2014). Each claim was assigned a single best dwelling together with a match-quality tier: a unit-level match (a unique candidate unit at the address), a building-level match (a unique building but an ambiguous unit), or unmatched. The dwelling-level analysis uses unit-level matches; the building-level matches are used in [robustness / the multi-dwelling analysis].

Across the ten events the procedure linked 4,523 of 6,013 compensation records to a dwelling, an overall match rate of 75% (Table 1). Match rates differ across events, but are most informative for the large events that dominate the sample — 78% for Bodil and 75% for the October 2023 surge — whereas the very small events yield volatile percentages, since a handful of unmatched records moves the rate substantially (Gorm comprises only six records). The main reason that a non-trivial share of claims cannot be matched is structural rather than technical: a compensation record refers to the policyholder’s *claim address*, which need not coincide with the address of the affected property but in most case does. Our objective throughout was to secure high-confidence matches and to minimize measurement error in the linked structural and elevation attributes, rather than to maximize the number of matched records. The staged design therefore deliberately favours precision over recall: ambiguous or low-confidence candidates are left unmatched rather than assigned, and the dwelling-level analysis is restricted to unit-level matches.

Table 1: Compensation records and matched dwellings, by storm-surge event.

Event	Claims	Matched	Match rate
Bodil (Dec 2013)	2,537	1,981	78%
Egon (Jan 2015)	59	55	93%
Gorm (Nov 2015)	6	2	33%
Urd (Dec 2016)	100	82	82%
Baltic surge (Jan 2017)	285	217	76%
Alfrida (Jan 2019)	62	40	65%
Ingolf (Oct 2021)	50	25	50%
Malik (Jan 2022)	29	20	69%
Baltic surge (Oct 2023)	2,713	2,020	74%
Pia (Dec 2023)	172	81	47%
Total	6,013	4,523	75%

Notes: Counts pool all dwelling types. Event dates to be verified against the Naturskaderådet declarations.

Figure 1 maps the compensated properties for the three largest events.

Bodil (December 2013) produced the broadest spatial footprint, with claims distributed along the North Sea coast of Jutland, the inner Danish waters around Funen and Zealand, and the southern Baltic shore. The two Baltic surges—January 2017 and October 2023—show a markedly different pattern, concentrated along the southern and eastern coasts of Jutland and the archipelago, consistent with wind-driven water set-up from the east. The geographic complementarity of the North Sea and Baltic events is visible in the figure and motivates the inclusion of event fixed effects in the regression models.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of compensated properties for the three largest storm-surge events. Each red dot marks a property with a positive payout. Baltic surge (Oct 2023): $n = 2,020$; Bodil (Dec 2013): $n = 1,981$; Baltic surge (Jan 2017): $n = 217$.

2.5 Elevation and hydrological exposure

Ground elevation at each dwelling was obtained by sampling Denmark’s national Digital Terrain Model — the $0.4\text{ m} \times 0.4\text{ m}$ DTM (DHM/Terræn, vertical datum DVR90) covering the entire country — at the dwelling’s coordinates (ETRS89 / UTM zone 32N, EPSG:25832). Because building locations are time-invariant, elevation was matched to all register vintages by unit identifier. We additionally computed Euclidean distances from each dwelling to the nearest coastline, harbor and large watercourse using GeoDanmark layers, with large streams identified by their width class. Combined with event-specific flood-height estimates, elevation yields the inundation depth at each property (Section 2.6). Dwellings are further assigned to coastal exposure zones. Storm-surge severity is governed by the sea area a stretch of coast faces—its tidal range, wind fetch, bathymetry and wave exposure—rather than by administrative boundaries, so the same water level implies very different flood risk across Danish waters. The Danish Coastal Authority’s high-water statistics reflect this by organising the coast into distinct sea areas (*farvande*), within which extreme water levels are statistically comparable (Kystdirektoratet, 2024). We follow this framework to construct a set of coastal exposure zones (see Figure 2). Each coastal municipi-

pality is assigned to the zone corresponding to the sea area its coastline faces, and zones are formed as unions of whole sea areas, so that each zone collects dwellings subject to a common surge regime. This yields [13] zones spanning the Danish coast, which enter the models as fixed effects in place of municipality indicators. The zones are our own aggregation of municipalities; they are informed by, but not lifted directly from, the Coastal Authority’s station-level statistics.

Figure 2: Overview of constructed coastal zones

2.6 Flood height and inundation depth

Storm-surge inundation depth is not recorded directly, so we reconstruct the water-surface elevation from the ground elevations of compensated properties. The key insight is that a dwelling receives compensation only if surge water reached it; conditional on a positive payout, its ground elevation is therefore a lower bound on the local water surface. Pooling across compensated properties ($payout_i > 0$), the upper tail of their elevation distribution reveals how high the water rose—zero-payout claims are excluded because they need not correspond to inundated properties and would bias the proxy downward.

Figure 3 illustrates this along a coastal slope: compensated dwellings (red) are flooded to a depth equal to the water level minus their ground elevation; properties above the water (grey) generate no claim. We estimate \hat{H} as a high

quantile of compensated-property elevations rather than the single maximum, so that one anomalously sited or misgeocoded property cannot dominate the estimate.

Figure 3: Reconstructing flood height from compensated-property elevations. Compensated (flooded) dwellings lie below the surge water surface; the 95th percentile of their ground elevations, $\hat{H}^{0.95}$, estimates the local water-surface elevation, and each dwelling’s inundation depth is $D_i = \hat{H} - E_i$, floored at zero. Schematic; elevations relative to DVR90.

Formally, let E_i denote the ground elevation (vertical datum DVR90) of dwelling i , sampled from the national 0.4 m digital terrain model (Section 2.5). For each storm event e and coastal exposure zone z , we estimate the flood height as a high quantile of the elevations of the *compensated* dwellings in that event–zone cell,

$$\hat{H}_{ez}^\tau = Q_\tau(\{E_i : i \in (e, z), \text{payout}_i > 0\}), \quad \tau \in \{0.90, 0.91, \dots, 0.99\}, \quad (1)$$

where $Q_\tau(\cdot)$ denotes the empirical τ -quantile. We compute the full set of quantiles $\tau = 0.90, \dots, 0.99$ (together with the sample maximum) as alternative flood-height definitions and adopt $\tau = 0.95$ as the baseline. Using a high quantile rather than the maximum guards against measurement error in the terrain model and in address geocoding, and against the occasional property compensated for damage unrelated to direct inundation; the flooring introduced below then ensures that dwellings lying above the estimated water surface contribute a depth of zero.

Because the precision of the proxy depends on the number of flooded observations, we resolve flood height spatially only where the data support it. Events with at least 200 compensated dwellings—Bodil, the January 2017 Baltic surge, and the October 2023 Baltic surge—are estimated at the coastal-zone level. The

remaining, smaller events are estimated at the event level by pooling all zones,

$$\widehat{H}_e^\tau = Q_\tau(\{E_i : i \in e, \text{payout}_i > 0\}). \quad (2)$$

For the large events, coastal zones containing fewer than 20 compensated dwellings were merged into the nearest adjacent zone within the same sea area until every estimation cell reached at least 20 observations, and a small number of isolated observations inconsistent with an event’s surge footprint—for example, a single Roskilde Fjord claim recorded under the otherwise Baltic October 2023 event—were dropped.

The inundation depth at each dwelling is then the estimated flood height in excess of its own ground elevation, floored at zero,

$$D_i^\tau = \max(\widehat{H}_{ez}^\tau - E_i, 0). \quad (3)$$

A property situated above the estimated water surface is assigned a depth of zero, whereas a property below it receives the vertical distance between the local water surface and its ground level. We use $D_i^{0.95}$ as the baseline depth measure and employ the remaining quantiles in robustness checks (Section ??).

The procedure rests on a planar approximation: it treats the water surface as spatially uniform within each event–zone cell and abstracts from within-zone gradients, wave run-up, and local flood defences. It also yields estimates only where compensated claims are observed. We therefore regard \widehat{H} as a transparent, data-driven proxy for local flood severity rather than a hydrodynamic reconstruction, and we assess the sensitivity of our results to the choice of quantile τ in Section ??.

Table 2 summarises the resulting baseline inundation depth, by storm event. Across events the typical depth is modest: median depths run from about 0.4 m for the smallest events to just over 2 m for the January 2017 Baltic surge, with most events centred on a median of 0.8–0.90 m. The two events that dominate the estimation sample, Bodil and the October 2023 Baltic surge, each have a mean depth close to 1m but pronounced right tails, with maxima of 3.7 m and 4.6 m respectively. This spread reflects the wide range of exposure within a large event, from marginally inundated dwellings sitting at or just below the estimated water surface—and therefore assigned near-zero depth—to a smaller set of severely flooded properties. The January 2017 Baltic surge stands out with the deepest typical inundation (median 2.1m), and Urd is also comparatively deep (median 1.4 m), whereas Ingolf is the shallowest (median 0.4 m); the remaining smaller events cluster around 0.7-0.9. The consistent right skew - every event’s maximum lies well above its median - is the expected signature of surge inundation, in which most compensated properties are flooded shallowly and a minority deeply. The cross-event differences are broadly consistent with the varying severity and spatial footprint of the events, which supports using 95th quantile as a property-level measure of flood exposure.

Table 2: Flood depth at the 95th quantile by storm event

Storm event	N	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
October 2023	1312	0.99	0.62	0	0.94	4.55
Alfrida	20	0.71	0.37	0	0.76	1.48
Bodil	1586	0.98	0.64	0	0.87	3.74
Egon	42	0.77	0.39	0	0.84	1.58
Gorm	1	0		0	0	0
Ingolf	19	0.36	0.17	0	0.42	0.65
Malik	9	0.79	0.42	0	0.84	1.35
Pia	37	0.86	0.40	0	0.94	1.51
Urd	49	1.29	0.45	0	1.42	1.80
Januar 2017	136	1.93	0.65	0	2.11	2.94

3 Empirical strategy

3.1 Specification

Let i index compensated dwellings, and let $e(i)$ and $z(i)$ denote the storm event and coastal exposure zone in which dwelling i is located. Let $y_i > 0$ be the payout. Dwelling size enters in logarithms, so that the corresponding coefficients can be interpreted as size elasticities. Inundation depth enters as $\log(D_i + 1)$, which allows us to retain compensated dwellings with zero modelled depth while preserving a proportional interpretation for changes in depth. The log-linear specification, estimated by OLS, is

$$\log y_i = \theta \log Size_i * \psi \log(D_i + 1) * \mathbf{x}'_i \boldsymbol{\beta} * \mathbf{w}'_i \boldsymbol{\phi} * \alpha_{e(i)} + \gamma_{z(i)} * \varepsilon_i, \quad (4)$$

where D_i is the reconstructed inundation depth (Section 2.6), $Size_i$ is the dwelling's size, $\mathbf{x} * i$ contains building-characteristic dummies, $\mathbf{w} * i$ contains distance-to-water bands, and $\alpha * e(i)$ and $\gamma * z(i)$ are storm-event and coastal-zone fixed effects. The generalized linear specification models the conditional mean of the payout in levels with the same linear index,

$$E[y_i | \cdot] = \mu_i, \quad \log \mu_i = \theta \log Size_i * \psi \log(D_i + 1) * \mathbf{x}'_i \boldsymbol{\beta} * \mathbf{w}'_i \boldsymbol{\phi} * \alpha_{e(i)} + \gamma_{z(i)}, \quad (5)$$

estimated by maximum likelihood with a Gamma family and log link.

The size measure is dwelling-type specific. For summer houses, $Size_i$ is the building footprint. In the pooled model for permanent dwellings, we let each type load on its natural size margin, entering $\log(\text{footprint})$ for detached houses and $\log(\text{unit area})$ for terraced houses through interactions with the dwelling-type indicators. The corresponding coefficients are therefore size elasticities within each type.

The coefficient on inundation depth, ψ , measures the response to changes in $\log(D_i + 1)$ rather than a constant elasticity with respect to D_i itself. For a change in depth from D_a to D_b , the implied proportional change in payout is $\left(\frac{D_b+1}{D_a+1}\right)^\psi - 1$. The percentage effect therefore depends on the initial depth. This specification retains compensated dwellings with zero reconstructed depth and avoids imposing an arbitrary positive offset.

3.2 Covariates

The vector \mathbf{x}_i collects building characteristics drawn from BBR. Size enters as the log building footprint — the ground-floor area exposed to inundation — together with the number of floors, which dilutes the share of the structure and contents located at ground level. A basement indicator captures the single most damage-relevant structural feature under surge flooding. Construction era is represented by period dummies (built before 1920, 1920–1960, 1960–1975, and 1975–2000, with post-2000 the omitted baseline), which proxy vintage differences in construction standards and materials as proposed by NIRAS (2023). Exterior wall material enters as dummies for light-concrete, half-timbered and wood construction, with brick the omitted baseline.

D_i is the inundation depth at the dwelling, the $q_{0.95}$ flood-depth measure defined in Section 2.6. We enter depth as using a natural log plus one transformation. We add one to the transformation to account for observation with a calculated zero inundation height. This choice of functional form allows the marginal damage of an additional metre of water to vary with depth: once the ground floor is fully inundated, further rise reaches progressively less vulnerable structure and contents, so a concave, saturating response is expected.

The vector \mathbf{w}_i contains distance-to-water band dummies (0–25 m, 25–50 m, 50–75 m and 75–100 m, with beyond 100 m the omitted baseline), which capture residual proximity effects — wave action, drainage and secondary inundation pathways — not already summarised by depth.

3.3 Fixed effects and identification

The terms α_e and γ_z are storm-event and coastal-zone fixed effects. Because most events contribute few compensated dwellings, the event effects are specified at the level of an event grouping: the three largest events (Bodil, the January 2017 Baltic surge, and the October 2023 Baltic surge) enter as their own levels and the remaining, smaller events are pooled into a single “minor events” category. The event effects absorb everything common to a given surge — its meteorological severity, duration and tidal timing, and the claims-handling and price environment of the corresponding year — so that identification does not rest on comparing a severe event with a mild one. The coastal-zone effects absorb time-invariant differences in coastal geomorphology, bathymetry and surge regime across sea areas, together with any zone-level differences in building stock or flood defences.

Identification of β , δ and ϕ therefore derives from variation across dwellings within the same event and the same coastal zone. The maintained identifying assumption is that, conditional on inundation depth, the water-distance bands, and the event and zone effects, the building characteristics in \mathbf{x}_i are uncorrelated with unobserved determinants of the payout (selection on observables). We interpret the estimates as the conditional association between each factor and the material cost of flooding — the drivers of realised damage, holding exposure and context fixed — rather than as strictly causal structural parameters. Two features qualify this interpretation. First, depth is an estimated proxy (Section 2.6) and the structural attributes are measured at the nearest BBR snapshot rather than the event date (Section 2.3), so the exposure and characteristic variables are measured with error. Second, the sample is conditioned on the existence of a compensated claim, so the estimates characterise damage among flooded, compensated properties and need not extrapolate to the broader population of coastal dwellings.

3.4 Estimation and inference

Both specifications are estimated with the fixed effects included as explicit regressors, so that the event- and zone-level coefficients are reported alongside the remaining parameters. Our baseline reports standard errors clustered at the municipality level, allowing for arbitrary correlation among dwellings in the same municipality — a shared local surge realisation, common loss assessors, and spatially correlated damage. We do not cluster on the coastal zone in the baseline, both because the small number of zones would render the cluster-robust variance unreliable and because the zone enters the model as a regressor.

4 Descriptive statistics

4.1 Descriptive statistics for single family & terrace houses

Table 3 and Table 4 describe the estimation sample of 1,022 single-family and terraced dwellings. The payout distribution is strongly right-skewed: mean compensation is about 465,000 DKK against a median of roughly 284,000 DKK, with a standard deviation larger than the mean and a maximum approaching 3 million DKK. This skew, characteristic of loss data, is what motivates the log-linear and Gamma specifications adopted below. The dwellings are moderately sized—a mean building footprint of 117 m² (median 110) and a mean total unit area of 149 m² (median 140)—the gap between footprint and unit area reflecting that many properties have more than a single storey. Estimated inundation depth averages 1 m (median 0.89 m) and reaches 3.7 m, with a group at zero for the properties that lie above the estimated water surface.

The structural and locational characteristics are reported as indicator shares in Table 4; because each group of dummies omits a reference category, the shares within a group do not sum to one. Basements are rare in this sample (3%). The

building stock is relatively old: about a quarter of dwellings were built before 1920 and a further 31% between 1920 and 1960, while only some 12%—the omitted category—date from after 2000. Brick is the dominant wall material and forms the omitted baseline at roughly three-quarters of the sample, with 15% timber and 11% other materials. Distance to water varies widely: the omitted reference of more than 100 m accounts for about 43% of dwellings, the 25-50 m band is the most common explicit category (23%), and only 9% sit within 25 m of the water.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics: continuous variables

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Median	Max
Payout (DKK)	1,022	465,495	512,052	5,232	284,489	2,998,129
Building footprint (m ²)	1,022	117.32	44.98	27	110	350
Unit size (m ²)	1,022	149.15	59.52	29	140	485
Flood depth q95 (m)	1,022	1.00	0.72	0.00	0.89	3.74

Table 4: Descriptive statistics: dummy variables

Statistic	N	Mean
Basement	1,022	0.03
Built before 1920	1,022	0.24
Built 1920–1960	1,022	0.31
Built 1960–1975	1,022	0.16
Built 1975–2000	1,022	0.17
Wall: other materiale	1,022	0.11
Wall: wood	1,022	0.15
Water dist. \leq 25 m	1,022	0.09
Water dist. 25–50 m	1,022	0.23
Water dist. 50–75 m	1,022	0.15
Water dist. 75–100 m	1,022	0.10

4.2 Descriptive statistics for summerhouses

Tables 5 and 6 describe the 1,957 summer houses in the estimation sample. As for the permanent dwellings, the payout distribution is right-skewed—mean compensation of about 480,000 DKK against a median of roughly 397,000 DKK and a maximum near 2.7 million DKK—though the gap between mean and median is markedly narrower than for single-family and terraced houses, indicating a less dispersed loss distribution. Summer houses are, as expected, considerably smaller: the mean building footprint is only 68 m² (median 64), little more than half the footprint of the permanent dwellings. Estimated inundation depth is

essentially the same as in the other samples, averaging 1.0 m (median 0.93 m) with a maximum of 4.6 m and a floor at zero for properties lying above the estimated water surface.

The indicator shares in Table 6 bring out the distinctive features of the summer-house stock; as before, each group of dummies omits a reference category, so the within-group shares do not sum to one. Wall material is the sharpest contrast with permanent housing: 81% of summer houses are of timber construction, against only 10% of other materials and brick—the omitted baseline—accounting for just 9%. The age profile reflects the post-war expansion of Danish summer-house areas, being concentrated in the 1960–1975 period (35%) and the preceding 1920–1960 period (25%), with a further 21% built between 1975 and 2000, only 3% before 1920, and 16%—the omitted category—after 2000. Summer houses also tend to lie further from the water than permanent dwellings: about two-thirds (67%) are more than 100 m from the nearest water (the omitted reference), while the 25–50 m band is the most common explicit category at 11% and only 6% lie within 25 m.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics: continuous variables

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Median	Max
Payout (DKK)	1,957	479,892.80	412,882.40	12,000.00	397,167.90	2,661,975.00
Building footprint (m ²)	1,957	67.91	26.56	18	64	382
Flood depth q95 (m)	1,957	1.02	0.60	0.00	0.93	4.55

Table 6: Descriptive statistics: dummy variables

Statistic	N	Mean
Built before 1920	1,957	0.03
Built 1920–1960	1,957	0.25
Built 1960–1975	1,957	0.35
Built 1975–2000	1,957	0.21
Wall: other materiale	1,957	0.10
Wall: wood	1,957	0.81
Water dist. \leq 25 m	1,957	0.06
Water dist. 25–50 m	1,957	0.11
Water dist. 50–75 m	1,957	0.08
Water dist. 75–100 m	1,957	0.08

5 Model Estimates

5.1 Damage cost estimates for single family houses & terrace houses

Table 7 reports estimates for the pooled sample of single-family and terraced houses. Column 1 reports the OLS model with log payout as the dependent variable, while column 2 reports the Gamma model with a log link for payout in levels. The two estimators agree closely in sign and magnitude throughout, and together the covariates account for about a third of the variation in log payouts ($R^2 = 0.33$). Because the dependent variable and the size regressors enter in logs, the size coefficients are elasticities. Depth enters as $\log(D_i + 1)$, so its coefficient captures the response to one-plus-depth rather than a constant elasticity with respect to depth itself. Dummy coefficients are interpreted as proportional effects of $\exp(\beta) - 1$ on the payout.

Flood depth is a driver of damage cost. The coefficient on $(\log(D_i + 1))$ is large and highly significant in both specifications ((1.17) and (1.06)), indicating that payouts rise strongly with inundation depth. Because depth enters as $(\log(D_i + 1))$, the coefficient is not a constant elasticity with respect to depth itself. The implied percentage effect depends on the initial depth. For example, increasing inundation depth from 1 m to 2 m is associated with an increase in expected compensation of about 61% in the OLS specification and 54% in the Gamma specification. Dwelling size matters as expected but more modestly: the footprint elasticity for single-family houses (0.37–0.41) and the unit-area elasticity for terraced houses (0.35–0.39) are of similar magnitude and significant in both columns, implying that doubling the relevant size measure raises payouts by roughly 30%.

Among the remaining building characteristics, the presence of a basement and the wall material stand out. A basement is associated with payouts about 95–110% higher, consistent with the additional, readily inundated below-grade space. Relative to the brick baseline, timber walls carry a 60–80% higher payout and other non-brick materials about 37% higher, suggesting that lighter or less flood-resistant construction translates into larger losses. The construction-era dummies reveal a partial vintage gradient: the two oldest cohorts attract lower payouts than the post-2000 baseline—the 1920–1960 cohort robustly so (about 30% lower in both columns) and the pre-1920 cohort significantly so only under OLS—while the 1960–2000 cohorts are statistically indistinguishable from the most recent dwellings. Building period therefore reflects damage cost only to a limited extent, with the oldest housing incurring the lower compensated losses.

The storm-event effects show that flood depth alone does not capture all variation in damage cost. Relative to Bodil, the October 2023 Baltic surge is statistically indistinguishable, whereas the January 2017 Baltic surge and the pooled minor events are associated with substantially lower payouts. This pattern suggests that the largest claim-generating events also tend to produce higher costs per affected property. The result may reflect several mechanisms. Large events may hit areas with more valuable or more vulnerable buildings, but

they may also differ in physical characteristics not captured by reconstructed depth, such as water velocity, wave energy, flood duration, debris, salinity, or contamination. Differences in warning, local flood experience, protective behaviour, claims settlement, and repair-market conditions may also matter. The event coefficients should therefore be interpreted as residual event-specific cost differences, not as pure measures of surge height or depth.

Finally, once inundation depth is controlled for, residual proximity to water adds little. None of the distance bands is robustly significant across both estimators—only the nearest (< 25 m) and the 75–100 m band reach significance under OLS alone—which is consistent with the flood-depth measure already capturing the relevant hydrological exposure and leaving distance to water with little independent explanatory power.

To assess which parts of the specification contribute most to model fit, we remove groups of related covariates one at a time. The groups are flood exposure, storm-event fixed effects, coastal-zone fixed effects, size and basement structure, wall material, and construction period. The largest reductions in explanatory power come from the contextual and exposure variables. In the OLS model, removing the storm-event fixed effects lowers (R^2) by 7.2 percentage points, followed by flood exposure at 6.0 percentage points and coastal-zone fixed effects at 5.6 percentage points. The building-level groups make smaller but still meaningful contributions: wall material lowers (R^2) by 1.8 percentage points, size and basement structure by 1.4 percentage points, and construction period by 1.2 percentage points. The Gamma model gives the same qualitative picture. Coastal zone, flood exposure, and storm event each reduce deviance explained by about 5–6 percentage points, while the building-characteristic groups contribute around 1–2 percentage points. These drop-one-group comparisons are not additive shares of total explained variation, but they show that most systematic variation in payouts is associated with exposure and event–coastal context, with building characteristics adding smaller but interpretable increments.

Table 7: Determinants of storm-surge payouts, single houses

	Storm-surge payout, single houses	
	OLS (log payout)	Gamma-log (payout)
	(1)	(2)
Log footprint (single)	0.368* (0.146)	0.407** (0.125)
Log unit size (terrace)	0.349* (0.147)	0.393** (0.120)
Basement	0.743*** (0.214)	0.667* (0.197)
Built before 1920	-0.346* (0.140)	-0.234 (0.133)
Built 1920–1960	-0.424* (0.170)	-0.341* (0.147)
Built 1960–1975	-0.141 (0.166)	-0.064 (0.137)
Built 1975–2000	0.004 (0.134)	0.025 (0.112)
Wall: other	0.312** (0.099)	0.317* (0.108)
Wall: wood	0.569*** (0.123)	0.487* (0.151)
Log flood depth	1.165*** (0.151)	1.063*** (0.146)
Dist. to water <25 m	0.358* (0.151)	0.307 (0.158)
Dist. 25–50 m	0.002 (0.117)	0.046 (0.103)
Dist. 50–75 m	-0.133 (0.130)	-0.124 (0.104)
Dist. 75–100 m	-0.166* (0.075)	-0.121 (0.099)
Event: Jan 2017	-1.558*** (0.282)	-1.328** (0.313)
Event: minor	-0.682** (0.257)	-0.621* (0.232)
Event: Oct 2023	0.048 (0.250)	0.058 (0.286)
Constant	11.273*** (0.650)	11.259 (14.941)
Coastal-zone FE	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,022	1,022
R ²	0.326	
Adjusted R ²	0.307	

Note:

*p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

OLS: municipality-clustered (CR1) SEs.

GLM: bias-reduced CR2 cluster-robust SEs with Satterthwaite dof.

Baselines: built after 2000; brick; >100 m; Bodil 2013; zone Lillebælt.

5.2 Damage cost Model Estimates for summerhouses

Table 8 reports the summer-house estimates, again from OLS on log payout (column 1) and the Gamma–log model on the payout level (column 2), over 1,957 dwellings with an R^2 of 0.30. As before, the logged coefficients are elasticities and the dummy coefficients approximate $\exp(\beta) - 1$ proportional effects.

Flood depth is again a central determinant of damage cost. The coefficient on $(\log(D_i + 1))$ is large and highly significant in both specifications. The estimates are larger in the OLS models than in the Gamma models, indicating a stronger response in the conditional geometric mean than in the conditional arithmetic mean. The flood depth coefficients are not constant elasticities with respect to depth itself. Instead, the implied percentage effect depends on the initial depth. The substantive result is nevertheless clear: payouts increase strongly with inundation depth in both dwelling segments. Dwelling size is also a robust driver. For summer houses, the footprint elasticity is about (0.47-0.46) and highly significant in both specifications, implying that a doubling of the footprint is associated with roughly (40%) higher payouts.

The other building characteristics are weak in this segment. Neither wall-material dummy is significant in either column—unsurprising given that the summer-house stock is overwhelmingly timber (Table 6), which leaves little variation to identify a material effect—and the construction-era dummies show no gradient: only the 1960–1975 cohort differs from the post-2000 baseline, attracting payouts about 18–23% higher, while all other vintages are statistically indistinguishable from it. Building period therefore carries little systematic information about damage cost here, beyond a single mid-century cohort that is hard to read as a genuine vintage effect.

The storm-event effects show that event context also matters for summer-house payouts. Relative to Bodil, the October 2023 Baltic surge is associated with much higher payouts, while the January 2017 surge and the pooled minor events are associated with lower payouts. The October 2023 effect is especially notable because it suggests that large claim-generating events can produce higher costs per affected summer house, even after controlling for reconstructed depth and coastal zone. As for permanent dwellings, this residual event variation may reflect several mechanisms. Large events may hit areas with more valuable or more vulnerable buildings, but they may also differ in physical characteristics not captured by depth, such as water velocity, wave energy, flood duration, debris, salinity, or contamination. Differences in warning, local flood experience, protective behaviour, claims settlement, and repair-market conditions may also contribute. The event coefficients should therefore be interpreted as residual event-specific cost differences rather than as pure measures of flood depth or surge height. Statistical support is strongest for the minor-events effect, which remains significant in both specifications, while the October 2023 and January 2017 effects are less precisely estimated under the Gamma model with CR2 standard errors.

Finally, as in the permanent-housing model, proximity to water has no independent effect once inundation depth is included: none of the four distance

bands is significant in either specification, reinforcing that the depth measure already absorbs the relevant hydrological exposure.

The drop-one-group comparisons give a similar picture for summer houses. We remove groups of related covariates one at a time: flood exposure, storm-event fixed effects, coastal-zone fixed effects, building size, wall material, and construction period. In the OLS model, the largest reductions in explanatory power come from the storm-event fixed effects and flood exposure, which lower (R^2) by 8.9 and 8.4 percentage points, respectively. Coastal-zone fixed effects follow with a reduction of 4.4 percentage points. Among the building-level variables, size is the most important, lowering (R^2) by 2.5 percentage points, while construction period and wall material contribute less than one percentage point each. The Gamma model gives the same qualitative ranking. Storm-event effects reduce deviance explained by 6.1 percentage points, followed by flood exposure at 4.4 percentage points, coastal zone at 3.7 percentage points, and building size at 3.2 percentage points. Construction period and wall material again add little. These drop-one-group comparisons are not additive shares of total explained variation, but they indicate that summer-house payouts are explained mainly by event context and flood exposure, with building size adding a smaller but meaningful contribution to explained variation.

Table 8: Determinants of storm-surge payouts, summer houses

	Storm-surge payout, summer houses	
	OLS (log payout)	Gamma-log (payout)
	(1)	(2)
Log footprint	0.473*** (0.068)	0.466*** (0.080)
Built before 1920	0.186 (0.132)	0.113 (0.163)
Built 1920–1960	−0.026 (0.079)	−0.020 (0.072)
Built 1960–1975	0.208** (0.072)	0.168* (0.060)
Built 1975–2000	0.131 (0.067)	0.066 (0.051)
Wall: other	−0.072 (0.143)	−0.109 (0.126)
Wall: wood	0.150 (0.107)	0.072 (0.095)
Log flood depth	1.381*** (0.161)	0.892*** (0.143)
Dist. to water <25 m	0.140 (0.140)	0.205 (0.126)
Dist. 25–50 m	−0.118 (0.082)	−0.084 (0.088)
Dist. 50–75 m	−0.033 (0.083)	−0.017 (0.071)
Dist. 75–100 m	−0.042 (0.053)	−0.078 (0.049)
Event: Jan 2017	−0.722* (0.314)	−0.718 (0.306)
Event: minor	−0.633** (0.204)	−0.505* (0.178)
Event: Oct 2023	0.914** (0.322)	0.692 (0.340)
Constant	9.217*** (0.475)	10.023*** (0.524)
Coastal-zone FE	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,957	1,957
R ²	0.295	
Adjusted R ²	0.286	

Note:

*p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

OLS: municipality-clustered (CR1) SEs.

GLM: bias-reduced CR2 cluster-robust SEs with Satterthwaite dof.

Baselines: built after 2000; brick; >100 m; Bodil 2013; zone Lillebælt.

6 Interpreting the estimated effects

The regression estimates in Tables 7 and 8 show that flood depth and building size are robust physical predictors of compensated storm-surge damage. This section translates these model estimates into predicted payout gradients. The purpose is to make the magnitudes of the estimated coefficients more interpretable in monetary terms. Figures 4a–4c show the predicted payout response for single-family and terraced houses, while Figures 4d and 4e show the corresponding gradients for summer houses. In all figures, the black line represents the predicted payout and the grey area shows the associated uncertainty interval.

6.1 Single-family and terraced houses

For permanent dwellings, the predicted payout rises strongly with reconstructed inundation depth. Figure 4a shows that a move from shallow flooding to several metres of inundation is associated with a large increase in expected compensation. The predicted curve rises from the lower hundreds of thousands of DKK at very shallow depths to around or above one million DKK at the upper end of the observed depth distribution. This illustrates the substantive meaning of the large and statistically significant coefficient on $\log(D_i + 1)$ in Table 7: flood depth is not only statistically important, but economically large.

The widening confidence interval at high depths in figure 4a reflects that few properties experience very deep inundation. The upper part of the curve should therefore be interpreted as evidence of a strong positive gradient, rather than as a precise prediction for any individual property.

Building size is also associated with higher predicted payouts, although the gradient is less steep than for flood depth; see Figures 4b and 4c. The figures show similar patterns for single-family and terraced houses: payouts increase with size, but at a decreasing rate. Substantively, this suggests that larger dwellings expose more structure and contents to floodwater, while each additional square metre adds progressively less to expected compensated damage conditional on flooding.

Taken together, the figures for permanent dwellings imply that flood depth is the dominant physical damage gradient, while size scales the resulting loss. A small dwelling experiencing deep flooding may therefore generate a larger payout than a much larger dwelling experiencing shallow flooding. This distinction is important for damage modelling and cost–benefit analysis, because it suggests that avoided depth and avoided exposure area enter the damage function through different mechanisms.

6.2 Summer houses

The summer-house estimates show a closely related pattern. Figure 4d shows that predicted payouts increase strongly with reconstructed inundation depth.

As in the permanent-dwelling model, the depth gradient is economically substantial: properties exposed to deep flooding are predicted to receive markedly higher compensation than properties exposed to shallow flooding. This supports the interpretation that inundation depth is the central transferable damage parameter across dwelling segments.

Figure 4e shows that the building footprint is also an important predictor for summer houses. The estimated size elasticity is somewhat larger than for permanent dwellings, implying that footprint is a particularly relevant exposure measure in this segment. As with single-family houses, the relationship is concave: larger summer houses have higher predicted payouts, but damage does not increase one-for-one with footprint.

Compared with permanent dwellings, the summer-house results also suggest that physical exposure variables explain more of the interpretable variation than detailed construction characteristics. This is consistent with the descriptive statistics, where the summer-house stock is more homogeneous in wall material and building style. In this segment, the main damage gradient is therefore primarily a function of how much water reaches the property and how much building area is exposed.

6.3 Implications for damage functions

The predicted effect curves highlight three broader implications for empirical flood-damage modelling. First, depth–damage relationships should not be treated as flat averages across flooded properties. Conditional payouts increase sharply with inundation depth, and this gradient is visible in both permanent dwellings and summer houses. Second, building size should be included explicitly, since larger exposed areas generate higher material losses even after controlling for depth, event, and coastal zone. Third, the sub-proportional size effects imply that simple damage functions based only on total building area may overstate the marginal damage of additional square metres if they assume a linear relationship.

The figures should be interpreted as conditional payout gradients for compensated properties, not as expected damages for all coastal dwellings. The analysis is conditioned on the existence of a positive compensation claim, and the payout measure captures compensated material damage rather than the full social cost of flooding. The estimates therefore describe how damage varies among affected and compensated properties. For policy applications, these gradients are most directly useful as empirical inputs to the intensive margin of a damage model: given that a dwelling is flooded and compensated, the predicted payout depends strongly on inundation depth and building size.

(a) Flood depth, single-family and terraced houses

(b) Footprint, single-family houses

(c) Unit size, terraced houses

(d) Flood depth, summer houses

(e) Footprint, summer houses

Figure 4: Predicted storm-surge payouts by flood depth and building size. The black lines show predicted payouts from the estimated models, while the grey areas show the associated uncertainty intervals. Panels (a)–(c) refer to single-family and terraced houses, and panels (d)–(e) refer to summer houses.

7 Discussion

The results provide a property-level account of how realised material damage from storm-surge flooding varies across dwellings and events. Three findings stand out. First, reconstructed inundation depth is the most consistent predictor of payouts. Second, storm events differ in their conditional cost even after controlling for depth and coastal zone. Third, building characteristics matter, but their role is more segment-specific than the role of exposure. Across separate models for permanent houses and summer houses, the evidence therefore points to a clear hierarchy: flood exposure is central, event context adds substantial residual variation, and building style contributes more selectively.

Inundation depth is the most consistent determinant across specifications. Because depth enters as one-plus-depth in logarithms, the coefficient is not a standard elasticity. The substantive result is nevertheless clear: payouts increase strongly with reconstructed inundation depth. This places the physical severity of flooding at the centre of damage cost, and it also lends credibility to the elevation-based flood-height reconstruction: a proxy built from the elevations of compensated properties nonetheless recovers a strong and stable relationship with the cost it is meant to explain. For damage models used in coastal adaptation appraisal, this is the key result: depth and building size are the most transferable empirical links between avoided flooding and avoided material cost.

The size of the event does appear to matter, but not in a simple way, and we can only speculate about why. Conditional on depth and location, payouts differ sharply across events: the deepest event (January 2017) carries among the *lowest* conditional costs, while October 2023 raises summer-house payouts well above the benchmark. The event effects should therefore be read as residual event-specific cost differences. They may reflect where the event occurred and which properties were hit, but also physical characteristics not captured by reconstructed depth, such as flood duration, wave energy, water velocity, debris, salinity, or contamination. They may also reflect warning, preparedness, local flood experience, claims settlement, and repair-market conditions. This result should give way to additional analysis exploring the possible factor driving the difference between large and small insurance payout events.

Building style influences cost unevenly. Among permanent houses, structure is clearly priced in—a basement roughly doubles the payout, and lighter (timber or other non-brick) walls carry markedly higher costs than brick—whereas among the near-uniformly timber summer houses, wall material is uninformative for want of variation. Construction era is the weakest of the three hypotheses throughout: permanent houses show only a mild tendency for the oldest cohorts to cost less, and summer houses no gradient at all beyond a single mid-century cohort. Vintage, we conclude, is at best a weak proxy for damage cost once size, materials and depth are accounted for.

These findings carry clear caveats. Payouts capture compensated material loss only and are a lower bound on the full social cost of flooding; the sample is conditioned on a compensated claim; depth is an estimated, spatially smoothed

proxy; and the event and coastal-zone effects rest on relatively few clusters. Subject to these qualifications, the analysis points to a policy-relevant core: The material cost of coastal flooding is driven first by reconstructed inundation depth and building size, with construction characteristics adding smaller, segment-specific contributions.

References

- Abate, T. G., Panduro, T. E., Massenberg, J. R., & Arnbjerg-Nielsen, K. (2026). *Do flood damage cost models predict real losses for residential buildings? Empirical benchmarking from Denmark and its implications for climate adaptation appraisal* (Environmental Social Science and Geography Working Paper Series). Roskilde, Denmark: Aarhus University, Department of Environmental Science.
- Colgan, W., Henriksen, H. J., Bennike, O., Riberio, S., Keiding, M., Karlsson Seidenfaden, I., ... others (2022). Sea-level rise in denmark: paleo context, recent projections and policy implications.
- Goyal, S., & Mukherjee, M. (2025). Flood-induced loss and damage estimation models: A state-of-the-art review. *IDRiM Journal*, 15(1). doi: 10.5595/001c.140542
- Kystdirektoratet. (2024). *Højvandsstatistikker 2024* (Tech. Rep.). Lemvig, Denmark: Kystdirektoratet (Danish Coastal Authority). Retrieved from <https://kyst.dk/klimatilpasning/vaerktoejer/hoejvandsstatistikker> (Revised November 2024)
- Lüdtke, S., Schröter, K., Steinhausen, M., Weise, L., Figueiredo, R., & Kreibich, H. (2019). A consistent approach for probabilistic residential flood loss modeling in Europe. *Water Resources Research*, 55(12), 10616–10635. doi: 10.1029/2019WR026213
- Naturskaderådet. (2025, July). *Naturskaderådets dækningsvejledning for skader som følge af stormflod, oversvømmelse og tørke* (Tech. Rep.). Author. (Senest opdateret juli 2025, Appendix B. Vejledning til taksatorer og sagsbehandlere til brug for opgørelse og behandling af stormflods-, oversvømmelses- og tørkeskader)
- NIRAS. (2023, December 21). *Hvornår trænger tag- og overfladevand ind i bygninger?* (Tech. Rep.). Miljøstyrelsen. (Projekt ID: 10419376. Udarbejdet for Miljøstyrelsen)
- Oppenheimer, M., Glavovic, B. C., Hinkel, J., van de Wal, R., Magnan, A. K., Abd-Elgawad, A., ... Sebesvari, Z. (2019). Sea level rise and implications for low-lying islands, coasts and communities. In H.-O. Pörtner et al. (Eds.), *Ipc special report on the ocean and cryosphere in a changing climate* (pp. 321–445). Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press. doi: 10.1017/9781009157964.006
- Porter, J. R., Marston, M. L., Shu, E., Bauer, M., Lai, K., Wilson, B., & Pope, M. (2023). Estimating pluvial depth–damage functions for areas within

- the United States using historical claims data. *Natural Hazards Review*, 24(1), 04022048. doi: 10.1061/NHREFO.NHENG-1543
- Steinhausen, M. (2022). *Probabilistic flood loss modelling for residential buildings* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin Berlin.
- Su, J., Andréé, E., Nielsen, J. W., Olsen, S. M., & Madsen, K. S. (2021). Sea level projections from ipcc special report on the ocean and cryosphere call for a new climate adaptation strategy in the skagerrak-kattegat seas. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 629470.
- Van der Loo, M. P. (2014). The stringdist package for approximate string matching.
- Vousdoukas, M. I., Mentaschi, L., Voukouvalas, E., Verlaan, M., & Feyen, L. (2017). Extreme sea levels on the rise along Europe's coasts. *Earth's Future*, 5(3), 304–323. doi: 10.1002/2016EF000505